
PHOTO ESSAY: RELIGIOUS LIFE IN BON SKOR,
AN A MDO TIBETAN COMMUNITY, PR CHINA
Rdo rje dpal 'byor རྫོག་རྗེ་དཔལ་འབྱུང་། (Duoji huanjiao 多吉环角)*

ABSTRACT

This photo essay documents religious activities and sites in Bon skor (Wangshenke) Community, Bya mdo (Shagou) Township, Mang ra (Guinan) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. Key aspects of community religious life include creating Buddhist clay images for stupas, turning prayer wheels, and offering butter lamps and water at a local *ma Ni* Hall where annual community religious rituals are held. Changes in local religious rituals are rapid, highlighting the value of this essay and its twenty-three images in recording local religious life in the first and second decades of the twenty-first century.

KEYWORDS

Amdo religious life, Amdo deity images, Tibetan prayer wheel, ma Ni Hall, Tibetan butter lamps

INTRODUCTION

Bon skor (Wangshenke) is an agro-pastoral Tibetan community in Bya mdo (Shagou) Township, Mang ra (Guinan) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China, located 200 kilometers (three hours by bus) from Zi ling (Xining) City, the Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) capital. Bon skor's five *ru khag* 'brigades' include four in the farming area and one in Dgon thang (twenty-six kilometers from the farming area) along the Rma chu 'Yellow River'. In 2007, the rise of the dammed Rma chu (Tshal rгна Reservoir 'Longyangxia') led Brigade Five to resettle near Mgo mang (Guomaying) Township Town, Mang ra County. In 2022, Bon skor had 2,200 residents and 570 households.

* Rdo rje dpal 'byor. 2023. Photo Essay: Religious Life in Bon Skor, an A mdo Tibetan Community, PR China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 63:288-314.

Locals tend sheep, goats, and cattle and cultivate wheat, barley, and canola. A few practice Bon, but most are Dge lugs Buddhist devotees. Residents hold multiple religious rituals collectively and privately every year for spiritual satisfaction, protection from illness and natural catastrophes, and strengthening of a sense of community.

FIG 1. Lha sgron rgyal (b. 1970) and her sister, Lha mo mtsho (b. 1972), at their sister's (G.yang ris, b. 1977) home to help make Buddhist images. *Bzang drug*¹ is added to *sa dmar* 'red soil' collected from Gong kha² to make a clay mixture for Buddhist images. Cleanliness is of paramount concern when involved in this activity. Participants wash their hands and wear disposable gloves and masks to avoid contaminating the clay. Chunks of clay are put in plastic bags until the next day to make kneading the clay easier (26 July 2022, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).³

¹ A medicinal, purifying powder made from six precious substances used in religious activities.

² A rich source of red soil in Mang ra County. Local *bla ma* consecrated that area and asked residents to use it to make images.

³ Rdo rje dpal 'byor, G.yang byam skyid, and G.yang ris took the photos in this essay in 2017 and 2022.

FIG 2. The following day, the three siblings (mentioned above) and their sister-in-law, Mi do (1986), pounded the clay with rubber mallets until it was smooth, thin, and flat. *Gzungs gzhus*¹ was placed under the clay, and *sku dpar*² was carefully positioned atop the flat clay pieces. One hand gripped the mold handle while the other struck the handle top with a mallet to imprint the images. Afterward, a sharpened piece of wood was used to remove extra clay around the clay images. A mold required frequent brushing and rubbing with canola oil to limit the clay sticking to the mold to ensure clear, intact images. Lha sgron rgyal (top right) holds a *sku dpar* (27 July 2022, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

¹ It generally refers to a few barley grains at the back of every image. High-ranking *bla ma* or monks give specific instructions. Papers with mantras were also used.

² A copper mold was used to make clay images.

FIG 3. Four women use a Tshe lha rnam gsum¹ mold to create images. Four images were simultaneously made on clay with less time and effort, and less soil was needed. The image features three divinities of longevity, Tshe dpag med at the top with two stupas on each side, Sgrol dkar on the left, and Gtsug tor rnam rgyal ma to the right (27 July 2022, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

¹ Three divinities of longevity: Tshe dpag med (Amitayus), Sgrol dkar (White Tara), and Gtsug tor rnam rgyal ma (Namgyalma)
<https://bit.ly/3M4qRHI> 3 October 2022.

FIG 4. This *sku dpar* is owned by Rnam 'bu's (b. 1972) family, who purchased it for 500RMB in a shop in Khri ka (Guide) that sold Buddhist-related items in 2014. Rnam 'bu made the *thod dkar* 'elm' frame. The metal end of the wooden handle reduced wear. A steel wire prevented cracking (27 July 2022, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

FIG 5. One thousand three hundred images of Tshe lha rnam gsum were dried for about twenty days before being placed in a stupa under construction at Ba kyA Monastery.¹ Many other local families each voluntarily made over 1,000 images to accumulate merit, stay safe, have long lives, and repel illness and bad fortune. Monks from Ba kyA are often invited to chant in local homes. Residents also sponsored the construction of a Ba kyA Assembly Hall and prayer wheels (27 July 2022, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

¹ Ba kyA dgon dar rgyas gling is located in Ba kyA Village, sixteen kilometers from Khri ka County Town. According to Nian and Bai (1993:189), it is a branch of La mo bde chen Monastery of Gcan tsha (Jianzha), a county in Rma lho (Huangnan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon Province. However, the local monks I consulted on 4 October 2022 told me the monastery was founded in 1827 by the second 'Ja' mo dkon mchog bstan 'dzin nyi ma (1791-1854). A lags snying nge was assigned to be the *bla ma* of this monastery in 1827. There were twenty monks in 2022. See Smith (2017:70) for a photo of the monastery.

FIG 6. This image of Mi 'khrugs pa (Rgyal ba mi 'khrugs pa), a supreme Buddhist being, is surrounded by a mantra locals chant to eliminate sins. Rnam 'bu's family made 1,000 images to put inside a stupa at the local nunnery¹ in the spring of 2022. Locals believe making this image helps eliminate misdeeds such as killing animals and harming other living creatures. Buddhist images such as Sgrol ma 'Tara', Ao rgyan rin po che (Padmasambhava 'Born from a Lotus'), and Tshe lha rnam gsum are also made based on what is required (2022, G.yang byams skyid).

¹ Bon skor jo mo dgon pa 'Bon skor Nunnery' had thirty nuns in 2022. It is located seven kilometers from the farming section of Bon skor. According to a local nun, it was founded in 2014. It is subsidiary to Tho le Monastery (Tho le dgon rnam rgyal phun tshogs chos rdzong gling), which was originally located in the Tho le area near the Rma chu in the northwest of Mang ra County, thirty-nine kilometers from the County Town. Founded by Dge 'dun bstan pa dar rgyas in 1916, it was a branch monastery of La mo bde chen Monastery. In 1984 after construction of Tshal rnga 'Longyangxia' Reservoir, the monastery was relocated to the northwest of the contemporary Mang ra Township. The monastery had thirty-four monks and one incarnation *bla ma* (Nian and Bai 1993:201).

FIG 7. These *gzungs gzhug* are for the Mi 'khrugs pa images. Mi 'khrugs pa mantras were wrapped with pine needles and *dar tshon sna lnga* 'threads of five colors' (yellow, red, green, white, blue) symbolizing *'byung ba lnga* 'the five elements' (earth, water, fire, air, space). A small hole was made at the back of the image in the heart area where the *gzungs gzhug* were placed inside. The opening was covered with clay (2022, G.yang byams skyid).

FIG 8. Lha sgron rgyal and G.yang ris used a mold with one hundred images of Klu dbang ryal bo 'Naga King'¹/'Nagaraja'² to make the 100,000 images required to build a '*bum khang*'.³ They ate no meat, garlic, or onion while engaged in this effort. Eating meat when associated with rituals involving water deities was forbidden for fear of offending these deities, as does the strong smell of garlic and onion. The women who made these clay images had health issues. One had rheumatoid arthritis, and the other often suffered from joint pain. *Mo ba* 'diviners' and local *bla ma* they consulted said they had offended *klu* 'naga'. Consequently, their families often asked monks or *sngags pa* 'tantric practitioners' to chant scriptures and hold rituals related to water deities that might help them improve. Both had collected firewood in a valley and played at water sources as children, which they believed had offended the *klu*.

The images they made were used to construct a '*bum khang*' near the community where a monk had designated a spring and selected a day for the ritual. Since it was a *klu*-related ritual, it was done on a *klu thebs* day – a day *klu* emerged from their retreats.

On the fifteenth day of the fifth lunar month of 2022, relatives carried clay images to the designated area with a water source at the upper side of the spring. A huge new fabric piece was spread on the ground, clay images were stacked on it, and the monk chanted. When it rained, the images disintegrated and flowed into the water source (2022, G.yang ris).

¹ Nagas were considered serpent spirits classified as one of the eight classes of gods and demons, or as animals or demi-gods who live beneath the earth's surface or in water, and in trees or rocks. Endowed with magical powers and wealth, they are responsible for certain illnesses transmitted to humans <https://bit.ly/3Dtr43B> 1 November 2022.

² Nagaraja's relationship with the nagas and spirits of the waterways, oceans, lakes, and the underworld explain why he was especially worshipped when diseases believed to be caused by nagas arose <https://bit.ly/3gEW7BO> 22 October 2022.

³ A religious practice requiring at least 100,000 clay images of one Buddha that are buried, or sometimes put in a stupa-like structure, with the help of a monk or several monks. A *bla ma* might also be engaged to chant during the ritual.

FIG 9. This Klu dbang rgyal bo mold featured a stupa on either side with mantras around the image. Lha sgron rgya bought it in 2021 at the suggestion of a monk (responsible for making 'bum khang near a water source). He said it was better to make images with a mold that had a single clear image since the mold with a hundred images was not very clear, so Lha sgron rgya bought it. This mold was also used to make 'chu dpar' water images' when the mold was repeatedly put into the water and removed. This was often practiced by locals near a spring or in a river. Lha sgron rgya and her sister made 300 images using this mold for a 'bum khang (27 July 2022, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

 RELIGIOUS SITE

FIG 10. The local *ma Ni* Hall is in the community's farming area. In 2016, the courtyard and gate were rebuilt with local contributions and community and religious leader management. A concrete road and steps were built, streetlamps were installed, and poplar and pine trees were planted around the yard. A stone lion was on either side of the steps (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

FIG 11. Prayer flags are on the back mountain as morning fog swirls around the *ma Ni* Hall. Rooms (L-R): a communal kitchen often used to cook for those who turned prayer wheels and participated in collective religious rituals such as fasting, chanting scriptures, and rituals to accumulate *tshogs* 'merit'.¹ The middle room allowed locals to sit and turn the prayer wheels and had seats and tables for meals. The green tile-roofed room had four large prayer wheels. Buddhist images and scriptures were on the shelves. Other rooms included a '*du khang* 'Assembly Hall', and five additional kitchens (one for each of the community's five brigades; six kitchens in total). There was also a room made from sheet metal for offering *mchod*

¹ A ritual held on the tenth and twenty-fifth days of each lunar month. Participants accumulated merit by chanting during this ritual.

me 'butter lamps' (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

FIG 12. The *ma Ni* Hall had four prayer wheels. One contained 100 million *ma Ni* script¹ built after the Culture Revolution when locals were at the community's former location (Bon po zhing kha).² The prayer wheel was brought to the current resettled location, and a small *ma Ni* room was built where the only prayer wheel was occasionally turned. Three prayer wheels made in Chab cha (Qiabuqia)³ with community patronage began to be rotated in the farming area on 15 October 2007. The prayer wheels have the *gzung gzhus* of the *Thar mdo* 'Liberation Scripture' and *Rdo rje gcod ba*,⁴ as well as around thirty different mantras. Each household spins the prayer wheels for twenty-four hours without pause about once every nineteen months since there were 570 households. In the event of a community member's death, the deceased's family could turn the prayer wheels (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

¹ The six syllables of the Avalokitesvara mantra are *oM ma Ni pad+me hUM*.

² Twenty kilometers from the current location and now submerged in Tshal rnga Reservoir.

³ The capital of Mtsho lho Prefecture.

⁴ The *Vajra Cutter Sutra* or *Diamond Sutra* <https://bit.ly/3fxeWGB> 1 November 2022.

FIG 13. Images of Ao rgyan rin po che (L), Thugs rje chen po (R), and other images were on the shelves, along with the multi-volume *Bka' 'gyur*¹ and *Bstan 'gyur*.² *Thang kha* and images of high-ranking *bla ma* were also displayed. Religious personages featured in photos were the ninth reincarnation of La mo gser khri chos kyi blo gros (b. 1969) (l) and the ninth reincarnation of La mo zhabs drung dkar po blo bzang bstan' dzin chos kyi rgyal mtshan (b. 1992) (r). Lamps and flickering artificial flowers were provided as offerings. Annually on the eighth day of the sixth lunar month, community members tied these scripture volumes to their backs with sashes. They circumambulated once around the community's farmland and houses, requiring about six hours (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

¹ Tibetan translations of the Buddha's own teachings
<https://bit.ly/3sQQox6> 2 November 2022.

² Commentaries on the Buddha's teachings <https://bit.ly/3ST18nv>
 November 2022.

FIG 14. Two local elders spun prayer wheels surrounding the *ma Ni* Hall. Religious leaders installed the prayer wheels with community members' financial support in 2016. Elders were the most frequent visitors to circumambulate, chant, and prostrate. They especially visited on the first, eighth, tenth, fifteenth, eighteenth, twenty-first, twenty-fifth, and thirtieth days of each lunar month. They prayed for good health, longevity, harmony between people, and removing misfortune. Locals lacquered the wheels when they lost paint, which was considered a great religious contribution (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

FIG 15. When their turn came to spin the prayer wheels, Bsod nam tshe bstan's family prepared butter for lamps, food, and water. At seven AM on 4 August 2022, Bsod nam tshe bstan and his wife, Khro mo, packed items in their car and traveled to the ma Ni Hall, where they took over from another family. Around nine AM, residents came to turn the prayer wheels, pulling on leather straps attached to the prayer wheels in another room. Locals often helped each other spin prayer wheels and, in return, had helpers when it was their turn. Helpers were needed, especially at night. They usually made groups of two or three and divided the hours for each group to turn the prayer wheels at night. Fruits, beverages, and snacks were often offered to the helpers. Locals gossiped if the prayer wheels stopped rotating (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

FIG 16. Lha sgrong rgya made *gro 'bras* 'wild yam rice' - wild yams, raisins, melted butter, and white granulated sugar with rice. The family responsible for prayer wheels on a certain day often offered lunch to those who helped turn the prayer wheels. *Rtsam pa*, cheese, butter, *gro 'bras*, and yogurt were typically provided. Eating meat in the *ma Ni* Hall was taboo (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

FIG 17. Khro mo fills disposable bowls with *hub ser*¹ 'cold wheat-flour noodles' drained and mixed with salt, oil, fried chopped *ke'u* 'chives', *sgog chu* 'minced garlic with liquid', vinegar, and chili powder, according to individual taste. Lha sgron rgyal and Lha mo mtsho also prepared tea and bread for lunch (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

¹ *Hub ser* is CT (Colloquial Tibetan) for a type of cold noodle.

FIG 18. Lunch. 'O ja 'milk tea', ja nag 'black tea', cung rdog¹ 'steamed buns', go re dmar po 'fried bread', fruit (watermelon, peaches) were on trays. Everyone was offered rtsam ba, gro 'bras, yogurt, and cold noodles based on their preference (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

FIG 19. A *bsang khri*² in the *ma Ni* Hall courtyard. The manager burned incense every morning to worship deities. Locals burned incense during religious rituals. They first made a fire with cow dung. When it stopped smoking, *bsang rtsi* 'incense material'³ was added. Tea or liquor was sprinkled on the incense and to the sky to beseech the deities for blessings and protection (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

¹ CT.

² A brick platform for burning *bsang* 'incense'.

³ LT (Literary Tibetan): *bsang rdzas* consisting of juniper leaves, and barley flour (main ingredients), granulated sugar, and fruit.

FIG 20. The *mchod pa* 'water-offerings' platform. The Buddhist images and decorations on the wall were made in 2022. The water offering ritual was initiated in 2017 after 2,500 *kong bu* 'butter lamp vessels', and 1,500 *dong bur*¹ 'water-offering bowls' were purchased with local contributions. Bzhi b'i smyung gnas 'Fasting Rite of the Fourth Month',² was held from the twenty-ninth day of the third lunar month to the fifteenth of the fourth lunar month. Mostly women residents fasting for sixteen days³ at the *ma Ni* Hall. Households were divided into *gshog ka* 'groups' of twenty to forty households based on family, *tsho ba* 'clan', or random assignment. Each group made water offerings, offering butter lamps, and serving those fasting for two days (4 August

¹ LT: *mchod kong*.

² See Pad+ma rig 'dzin (2021:47-73) for a description of an A mdo Smyung gnas.

³ A fasting ritual typically held for two days. On the first day, participants were free to have lunch and a cup of milk tea in the evening. On the second day, participants only chanted and were forbidden to have food and drink, and talk with others. This continued until the next morning. At dawn, they had *thor thug* 'sweet milk-flour soup'. This sixteen-day ritual consisted of eight fasting periods locals referred to as *smyung gnas chog brgyad* 'eight fasting rituals'. Participants practiced based on their ability and time. They were not required to fast a certain number of times. Some fasted for sixteen days, while others fasted intermittently.

2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

FIG 21. A group of people offered water with kettles in the *ma Ni* Hall. The water-offering receptacles were put in order in straight lines. The space between bowls ideally was the size of a barley grain. Water was carefully poured into the bowls without spilling.¹ Once all the bowls were filled, five to ten minutes passed. The bowls were then emptied and rubbed with a cloth. This process was repeated to offer as much water as possible. Klu mo rgyal (b. 1965) said, "Around 10,000 bowls of water can be offered a day if many people are involved."

As the local saying goes:

TEXT AS SPOKEN

ཡར་དཀོན་མཚོག་ག་མཚོད་པ།

མར་དབུལ་བོར་སྦྱིན་པ།

yar dkon mchog ga mchod pa,

¹ According to community resident, Lha sgron (b. 1946), an appropriate amount of water was to be poured into the offering bowls. If the bowl overflowed, the person responsible was in danger of losing control of their saliva or mucus flow in the next life. If the water was too little, a very poor next life was a possibility.

mar dbul bor sbyin pa.

LITERARY POETIC TEXT

ཡར་དགོན་མཚོག་ལ་མཚོང་པ།

མར་དབུས་བོ་ལ་སྦྱིན་པ།

yar dkon mchog la mchod pa,

mar dbul bo la sbyin pa.

ENGLISH TRANSLATION

Provide offerings to the Jewels,¹

Offer donations to impoverished people.

Water offerings help prevent famine and bring wealth in the next life (2017, Rdo rje dpal byor).

¹ The Three Jewels (the Buddha, dharma, and sangha).

FIG 22. A local elder melted *mchod mar* 'butter for offering' (margarine bought from the township town used to make *mchod me*). Locals often offered butter lamps at the *ma Ni* Hall during rituals (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

FIG 23. Women made *mchod me* in a room built for lit butter lamps. They first made *sdong ras* 'wicks' (thin *sdong rtswa* 'grass stalks' wrapped with cotton). The length and thickness depended on the size of the butter lamp vessel. The end of the wick in the small hole at the vessel's center was thicker than the upper part. Melted butter was poured into the butter lamp vessel and on the wick so it would readily light. Butter lamp vessel names were based on their size. For example, a *mtshan thub* was a butter lamp that burned all night, and a *tshe 'bar* was a large one that burned for around ten days and nights (4 August 2022, Rdo rje dpal byor).

TIBETAN TERMS

'bum khang འབྲུམ་ཁང་།

'du khang འདུ་ཁང་།

'o ja འོ་ཇ།

'ja' mo dkon mchog bstan

'dzin nyi ma

འཇའ་མོ་དཀོན་མཚོག་བསྟན་འཛིན་ཉི་མ།

a lags snying nge

ཨ་ལགས་སྙིང་ངེ།

Avalokitesvara, spyan ras

gzigs ལྷུན་རས་གཟིགས།

Padmasambhava, ao rgyan

rin po che མོ་རྒྱན་རིན་པོ་ཆེ།

'byung ba lnga འབྱུང་བ་ལྔ།

ba kyA dgon dar rgyas gling

བ་ལྷ་དགོན་དར་རྒྱས་གླིང་།

bka' 'gyur བཀའ་འགྲུས།

bla ma ལྷ་མ།

bon po zhing kha བོན་པོ་ཞིང་ཀ།

bon skor བོན་སྐོར།

bon skor jo mo dgon pa

བོན་སྐོར་ཇོ་མོ་དགོན་པ།

bsang བསང་།

bsang khri བསང་ཁྲི།

bsang rdzas བསང་རྩས།

bsang rtsi བསང་རྩེ།

bsod nams tshe bstan

བསོད་ནམས་ཚེ་བསྟན།

bstan 'gyur བསྟན་འགྲུས།

bya mdo བྱ་མདོ།

bzang drug བཟང་དུག

bzhi b'i smyung gnas

བཞི་བའི་རླུང་གནས།

chab cha ཆབ་ཇ།

chu dpar ལྷ་དཔལ།

cung rdog ལུང་རྟོག (CT)

dar tshon sna lnga དར་ཚོན་སྣ་ལྔ།

dgon thang དགོན་ཐང་།

dge 'dun bstan pa dar rgyas

དགེ་འདུན་བསྐྱེད་པ་དང་རྒྱལ།

dge lugs དགེ་ལུགས།

dong bur རོང་བུར།

g.yang byams skyid

གཡང་བྱམས་སྦྱིད།

g.yang ris གཡང་རིས།

gcan tsha གཅན་ཚ།

gcod ba གཅོད་པ།

go re dmar po གོ་རེ་དམར་པོ།

gong kha གོང་ཁ།

gro 'bras གྲོ་འབྲས།

gshog ka གཤོག་ཀ།

gtsug tor rnam rgyal ma

གཏུག་རྟོར་རྣམ་རྒྱལ་མ།

gzungs gzhug གཟུངས་གཞུག།

hub ser (CT) ལུབ་ལེར།

ja nag ཇ་ནག།

jo mo dgon pa ཇོ་མོ་དགོན་པ།

ke'u ཀེ་ལ།

khri ka ཀྲི་ཀ།

khro mo ཀྲོ་མོ།

klu ལུ།

klu dbang rgyal bo

ལུ་དབང་རྒྱལ་བོ།

klu mo rgyal ལུ་མོ་རྒྱལ།

klu thebs ལུ་ཐེབས།

kong bu ཀོང་བུ།

la mo bde chen ལ་མོ་བདེ་ཚེན།

la mo gser khri chos kyi blo

ལ་མོ་གསེར་ཀྲི་ཚོས་ཀྱི་བློ་གྲོས།

la mo zhabs drung dkar po blo

bzang bstan 'dzin chos kyi

རྒྱལ་མཚན་མཚན།

ལ་མོ་ཞབས་དྲུང་དཀར་པོ་བློ་བཟང་བསྐྱེད་འཛིན་ཚོས་

ཀྱི་རྒྱལ་མཚན།

lha mo mtsho ལྷ་མོ་མཚོ།

lha sgron ལྷ་སྒོན།

lha sgron rgyal ལྷ་སྒོན་རྒྱལ།

ma Ni མ་ཤེ།

mang ra མང་ར།

mchod kong མཚོད་ཀོང།

mchod mar མཚོད་མར།

mchod me མཚོད་མེ།

mchod pa མཚོད་པ།

mgo mang མགོ་མང།

mi 'khrugs pa མི་འཕུགས་པ།

mi do མི་དོ།

mo ba མོ་བ།

mtshan thub མཚན་ཐུབ།

mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྒོན།

Naga, klu ལུ།

Nagaraja, klu dbang ryal bo

ལུ་དབང་རྒྱལ་བོ།

oM ma Ni pad+me hUM

ཨོ་མ་ཤེ་པ་ལྷོ་ལྷོ།

rdo rje dpal byor

རྩོ་རྗེ་དཔལ་འབྱོར།

rdo rje gcod ba རྩོ་རྗེ་གཅོད་པ།

rgyal ba mi 'khrugs pa

རྒྱལ་བ་མི་འཕུགས་པ།

rma chu མ་ཅུ།

rma lho མ་ལྷོ།

rnam 'bu རྣམ་འབུ།

rtsam ba རུས་པ།

ru khag རུ་ཁག།

sa dmar ས་དམར།

sdong ras སྣང་རས།

sdong rtswa སྣང་རྩ།

sgog chu སྒོག་ཅུ།

sgrol dkar སྒོལ་དཀར།

sku dpar སུ་དཔར།

slob dpon rin po che

སློབ་དཔོན་འིན་པོ་ཆེ།
smyung gnas chog brgyad
 སློང་གནས་ཚོག་བརྒྱད།
sngags pa ལྷགས་པ།
Tara, sgröl ma སྤྲོལ་མ།
thar mdo ཐར་མདོ།
tho le ཐོ་ལེ།
tho le dgon rnam rgyal phun
tshogs chos rdzong gling
 ཐོ་ལེ་དགོན་རྩམ་རྒྱལ་ལུན་ཚོགས་ཚོང་གླིང་།
thod dkar ཐོད་དཀར།
thor thug ཐོར་ཐུག།
thugs rje chen po
 ཐུགས་རྗེ་ཆེན་པོ།
tshal rnga ཐཤ་རྩ།
tshe 'bar ཐེ་འབར།
tshe dpag med ཐེ་དཔག་མེད།
tshe lha rnam gsum
 ཐེ་ལྷ་རྩམ་གསུམ།

tsho ba ཐོ་བ།
tshogs ཐོགས།
Vajra Cutter, rdo rje gcod ba
 རྩ་རྗེ་གཙོང་པ།

CHINESE TERMS

Guide 贵德
Guinan 贵南
Guomaying 过马营
Hainan 海南
Huangnan 黄南
Jainzha 尖扎
Longyangxia 龙羊峡
Qiabuqia 恰卜恰
Qinghai 青海
Shagou 沙沟
Wangshenke 汪什科
Xining 西宁